

Project number: 101113620
Acronym: LIFE22-CCA-IT-LIFE VitiCaSe
Title: Viticulture for Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration

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Call:	LIFE-2022-SAP-CLIMA		
Project Number	101113620		
Project full name	Viticulture for Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration		
Project acronym	LIFE22-CCA-IT-LIFE VitiCaSe		
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Deliverable Number	D.4.1	Lead Beneficiary	CREA
Deliverable title	Characterisation of Pilot farms (soils, management and pedo-climate)		
Type	R – Document, report	Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Due Date (month)	12	Work Package No	WP 4
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Executive summary

This document describes the characterization of the pilot farms and includes a detailed analysis of their soil characteristics, management practices, and pedoclimatic conditions.

Farms were characterized using comprehensive datasets including climate, soil, and crop management information collected from both international databases and field data. Climatic data such as temperature and precipitation were obtained from global climate databases, while soil properties were analysed regionally, focusing on factors such as soil texture and organic matter content, which are directly related to soil carbon stock. Crop management practices, including fertilizer and pest control strategies, were documented through detailed farm surveys.

The interaction between soil and local climatic conditions provides a deeper understanding of how farms adapt to and are affected by environmental change, enabling the development of tailored solutions for sustainable carbon farming.

Introduction

The main objective of WP4 in LIFE VitiCaSe is to test and apply in vineyards the sustainability (technical feasibility and economic viability) of a business model based on C-farming and to use the innovative C-farming IT tool developed in WP3 to quantify or estimate the improvements in SOC levels.

The Work Package 4 is structured in the following way:

T4.1 – Define the baseline management (Business as usual) for each farm

T4.2 – Soil carbon baseline management

T4.3 – Operational design of pilot actions

T4.4 – Implementation of pilot actions

This report constitutes Deliverable 4.1 of the VitiCaSe project which aims to set up the baseline (business as usual), by providing an overview of the status of the 4 pilot farms in the Veneto and Toscana regions (Fig. 1).

The baseline conditions in the different pilot farms will be characterised, by taking into account the description of the different site locations, the actual soil management practices, and the pedo-climatic characteristics. A detailed description of the data collected is given in the following sections.

Figure 1 - Location of pilot areas of the “VitiCaSe” project.

1- Materials and Methods

1.1 Data management

The pilot farms were characterized using a comprehensive set of data, including climatic conditions, soil properties, and crop management practices. Data was collected from a combination of international and regional databases and by gathering field data directly from the farms. Climate data such as temperature and precipitation were sourced from global climate databases, while detailed soil descriptions—covering aspects like texture and soil organic content—were performed at a regional level. Additionally, data on crop management, including fertilizer use and pest control strategies, were meticulously recorded through farm surveys. This integrated approach ensured a thorough understanding of the unique environmental and operational conditions of each farm, providing a solid foundation for further analysis and decision-making on sustainable farming practices.

1.2 Common references for soil characteristics description

1.2.1 Soil data in Tuscany

To identify the key soil characteristics in the different pilot farms, we used the dataset “Soil Database of the Tuscany Region¹”. It contains geometric and semantic information on the characteristics and qualities of the different soils, organized by typology and by cartographic units. Based on the recognition of the soil characteristics, starting from an analysis of the morphological, physiographic and geological characteristics, from various analyses carried out based on statistical sampling criteria and from a detailed study based on photointerpretation, it was possible to compile² the following.

Database of Soil-landscapes, structured on 4 levels of study:

- I. The Soil Regions are defined at a European scale;
- II. The Systems defined at a national scale;
- III. The Subsystems defined at the regional scale for a classification at the recognition scale;
- IV. The Landscape Units (LU) are defined at the regional scale for classification at the semi-detailed scale.

Each LU at the semi-detailed scale and each Subsystem at the recognition scale corresponds to a specific Soil reference Cartographic Unit representing its pedological connotation in the form of a

¹ Available at <https://www502.regione.toscana.it/geoscopio/pedologia.html>

² Detailed description on the Technical and methodological procedures for the realization of soil surveys in the countryside and for the realization of Landscape Units (UDP), Cartographic Units (UC) and Typological Units and Subunits of soil (UTS and STS) for the Soil Database of the Tuscany Region, are available at

https://geoblog.regione.toscana.it/documents/11974914/12673503/Procedure_tecniche_e_metodologiche_di_rilevamento_pedologico_RT.pdf/315919ea-7f91-4e45-9f76-f94dd665516e?t=1434714266406

consociation or association of soils. Therefore, the set of pedological delineations or polygons characterized by the same pedological content can be defined as cartographic units.

1.2.2. Soil data in Veneto

We used the dataset namely “Soil Map at 1:50,000 scale” to identify the key soil characteristics from the Veneto Region³. The legend of the Soil Map at 1:50,000 scale is harmonized within the region and represented in a single document, referring to the part of the Veneto territory mapped at the semi-detailed scale⁴.

The legend is divided into four hierarchical levels:

- I. DISTRICT: distinguishes the large territorial areas: plain, hilly or mountainous relief.
- II. LANDSCAPE OVERUNITY: distinguishes the territory based on the characteristics that have influenced the development of the soils.
- III. SOIL LANDSCAPE UNIT: it is defined based on the morphology of the surfaces: hummocks, depressions, slopes with different gradients, etc.
- IV. CARTOGRAPHIC UNIT: portions of territory homogeneous in the presence and distribution of soils.

1.3 Common references for soil characteristics description

Soil organic matter (SOM) is the living material and residue of biological origin (dead material) present in the soil and is commonly used in soil quality assessment systems. In any ecosystem, a steady-state SOM content is reached when carbon inputs to the soil as organic residues match losses through respiration, leaching and erosion. Typically, the Soil Organic Content (SOC), the major component of SOM, in agricultural soils is much lower than in undisturbed soils of the same type. In addition to its effect on the chemical and physical properties of soil affecting plant growth, the main biological functions of SOC are to provide a substrate for a wide range of soil organisms and a source of nutrients for plants through mineralisation and stabilising enzyme activities. It is difficult to assign minimum or maximum threshold values for SOC in viticulture, particularly as SOC varies widely between soil types, and interpretative criteria that are meaningful to vine performance are not readily available. Criteria adapted from the literature to indicate low, medium and high levels of SOM for topsoils of different agricultural soil textures in Italy, are shown in Table 2. However, in the absence of more specific data related to vineyards, these values can be used only as a first approximation for comparing blocks within a vineyard or between vineyards on the same or similar soil type. Comparison with undisturbed soils of the same type is unsuitable for setting a benchmark, because the equilibrium SOM content of long-term grassland or forest may not be achievable for a vineyard soil, even under best management practices.

³ Available at <https://gaia.arpa.veneto.it/maps/778>

⁴ Detailed description on the Technical and methodological procedures for the realization of the Soil Map are available at <https://www.arpa.veneto.it/temi-ambientali/suolo/conoscenza-dei-suoli/carte-1-50.000/legenda-carta-dei-suoli>

Instead, it may be more helpful to define a minimum SOM content (a threshold) below which desirable soil characteristics, productivity and ecological functions suffer and cannot be restored within a reasonable time.

Based on the Land Capability Classification (LCC) – available in both regions – and USDA Soils classification, all vineyards in the pilot farms are classified according to their SOC level based on the value shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Classification of soil organic matter in agricultural soils of different textures in Italy.

SOC Class	Soil organic matter (%)			SOC Class
	Sandy soils (S-SF-FS)	Loam (F-FL-FA-FAS)	Clay loam/clay (A-AL-FLA-AS-L)	
Very low	<0,8	<1,0	<1,2	Low
Low	0,8-1,4	1,0-1,8	1,2-2,2	
Moderate	1,5-2,0	1,9-2,5	2,3-3,0	Medium
High	>2,0	>2,5	>3,0	High

1.4 Climatic data

The climatic data source is the Global Data Assimilation System (GDAS), which is the system used by the Global Forecast System (GFS) model to place observations into a gridded model space to start, or initialise, weather forecasts with observed data. The climate database is an integrated mesoscale re-analysis of the Central Mediterranean. In this study, mean air temperature and rainfall data for the period 2013-2023 were considered. Data are related to the location point described in Table 2 for each farm.

Table 2- Location of climatic data for the different pilots.

Farms	Municipality	Province	Coordinates
Ruffino	San Donà di Piave	VE	45.672424, 12.595862
Castello d'Albola	Radda in Chianti	SI	43.519389, 11.403175
San Felice	Castelnuovo Berardenga	SI	43.387900, 11.458694
Montemassi	Roccastrada	GR	42.950379, 11.057446

2- Pilot farms in Tuscany

2.1 Farm 1: Castello di Albola s.a.r.l. (ALBOLA)

Figure 2 – Castello d'Albola's farm centre in Radda in Chianti (SI).

Site

"Castello di Albola is a vineyard farm located in Castello d'Albola, Radda in Chianti, in the province of Siena (Figure 2). It extends for 790 hectares, of which over 106 ha are devoted to vines for the production of Chianti Classico DOCG, 10 ha to olive groves, and the rest to woods.

The "Albola" farm adopts organic farming, the main varieties grown are Sangiovese and Chardonnay. The form of breeding is guyot, with a distance between rows of 2.5 m and an intra-row of 0.8 m. The average number of vines is 5000 per hectare.

The farm has provided approximately 50 hectares of vineyards to the project (Figure 3), with 62% planted with Sangiovese, 6.4% of Chardonnay, and the remaining area dedicated to a mix of Sangiovese and Cabernet Sauvignon.

Figure 3. Albola vineyards included in the VitiCaSe project

Pedo-climate information

Soils description

The vineyards of “Albola”, involved in the project, are located in the Soil region named “APP- Rilievi montuosi dell’Appennino settentrionale e centrale”, inside the sub-systems 55, 61, and 123 (Figure 4).

Table 2 shows the soil characteristics of the different systems and sub-systems of the “Albola” pilot area.

Figure 4 - Soil subsystems in the Albola vineyards.

Table 2. Key Soil Characteristics of Castello di Albola

Soil Region	System	Subsystem	Main key soil properties
APP: Mountainous reliefs of the Northern and Central Apennines	APP7. Mountainous surfaces with moderate slopes and hilly surfaces of high and low altitude with moderate to steep slopes, on a substrate consisting mainly of clay with predominantly agricultural use (permanent meadow, arable land, olive grove and vineyard) and secondarily woodland (beech coppice, mixed coppice of thermophilic deciduous broadleaf trees, coniferous forest). Udic and ustic, mesic soil and climate regime.	55. Linear slopes, sometimes terraced, with a low to high gradient, subject to moderate to high widespread water erosion and sometimes to mass erosion; heterogeneous substrate consisting mainly of clays and marls with limestones (Undifferentiated Complex, Chaotic and Scaly Clays); land use consisting mainly of olive groves, vineyards, alternate arable land and, secondarily, pasture, shrubland, mixed forest.	Soil reference: GCC1 Clay content: 29.15 Organic matter (%): 1.49
	APP_4. Mountainous areas of medium to high altitude, very steep and medium and high-altitude hills with steep slopes, on a substrate consisting of arenaceous pelitic flysch and deposits generated by it, used mainly for forestry (chestnut coppice and beech coppice) and secondarily for agriculture (olive grove, vineyard). Udic and ustic, mesic soil and climate regime.	61. Slopes with valleys, from steep to steep, subject to moderate to strong diffuse and channelled surface erosion, with the presence of accumulation areas with lower slope; substrate consisting mainly of sandstones (Macigno type "A"); land use consisting mainly of mixed coppice of deciduous broadleaf trees, secondarily of coniferous woods and, marginally, of arable land and olive groves.	Soil reference: VIL1 Clay content: 41 Organic matter (%): 1.54
	APP_6. High and medium altitude hilly surfaces with moderate to steep slopes, on a substrate mainly composed of marly calcareous flysch, mainly used for coppice woodland (downy oak, Turkey oak) and secondarily for agriculture (olive grove, vineyard). Ustic and udic, mesic soil and climate regime.	123. Incised slopes, moderately sloping to steep, generally eroded to very eroded in the medium-high parts, terraced in the medium-low and low parts; substratum consisting mainly of marly limestones, marl schists and calciferous sandstones (Alberese) and marly limestones (Sillano Formation); land use consisting mainly of vineyards, olive groves, degraded mixed broadleaf forest.	Soil reference: GRT1 Clay content: 12.3 Organic matter (%): 1.5
			Soil reference: CLV1 Clay content: 26.2 Organic matter (%): 2.1

Figure 5. Soil carbon content classes in the Albola vineyards.

Based on the USDA soil reference classification (Table 2), the soil texture of the representative soils of the different subsystem units is mainly clay-loam, with a clay content range from 12.3% to 41% and a SOC content ranging from 1.4 to 2.1%, which means that these soils have a low to medium SOC content based on Table 1.

Climatic description

The climate in this area is typical hot-summer Mediterranean (Köppen classification: Csa) characterized by warm dry summers, mild winters, and with rainfall mainly concentrated in autumn and spring.

Figure 6 shows the weather conditions from 2013 to 2023. In the last 3 years, it has been highlighted that mean temperature has increased and rainfall has decreased below 1000 mm/year. In the period

considered, the daily minimum mean temperature was $-6,6^{\circ}\text{C}$ (27/2/2018), the maximum of $27,9^{\circ}\text{C}$ (3/8/2017), and the mean temperature of $11,9^{\circ}\text{C}$. The mean annual precipitation is 1076 mm: the higher annual precipitation was registered in 2014 with 1457 mm, and the minimum in 2017 with 696 mm.

Figure 6 - Annual mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and rainfall (mm) from 2013 to 2023 in the area.

Management

The farm holds both organic and “Equalitas” certifications and is covered by multi-risk insurance for its crops.

The practices currently adopted in the vineyards can be described as follows:

- Minimum tillage in 50% of the area;
- Spontaneous grass cover and Leguminosae cover crop in alternate rows: one row with grass cover and another with 1 leguminous species, usually filed bean (‘Favino’).
- Manure application: the areas where the manure is applied vary according to weather conditions.

All vineyards are subjected to the following practices:

- Organic fertilisation;
- Use of fungicides allowed in organic farming;
- Use of pesticides of natural origins allowed in organic farming;
- Reuse of wood residues in the field without burning;
- The vineyards are not irrigated;
- The harvest is both mechanical and manual.

The farm uses third party contractors for the manual management of greenery and dry pruning.

Table 3 reports the man-hours used to manage the crop each year.

Table 3 - Man hours for the different crop operations in Albola.

Crops operations	Man/hours per hectare
Mechanical processing and mechanical treatments	60 hours/hectare
Manual Green Management	130 hours/hectare Of which: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 74 hours/hectare farm• 56 hours/hectare subcontracted
Manual dry pruning	90 hours/hectare Of which: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 50 hours/hectare farm• 40 subcontracted
Ordinary maintenance	30 hours/hectare
Mechanical harvest	7 hours/hectare on 80 hectare
Manual harvest	35 hours/hectare on 25 hectare

Sustainable Soil Management (SSM) Practice adopted in LIFE VitiCaSe project

The farm chose to adopt the following SSM practice:

- Minimum tillage
- Enhance spontaneous grass cover with Leguminosae
- Improve mulching of pruning residues

Contact

Manager: Alessandro Gallo (Director and oenologist)

Advisor: Jacopo Ferrari (Agronomist)

Other contacts: Marianna Cavaciocchi

Website: <https://albola.it/>

2.2 Farm 2: San Felice SpA (SAN FELICE)

Figure 7 - San Felice vineyards.

Site

Agricola San Felice Spa is a wine-growing company situated in Castelnuovo Berardenga, in the province of Siena, in the Chianti DOC area (Figures 7 and 8).

San Felice extends over 600 hectares: 152 hectares of vineyards, most of which are used to produce Chianti Classico DOCG, 80 ha of olive groves with more than 15,000 trees, and woods.

The farm adopts organic farming and the main vines grown are Sangiovese and Pugnitello. The type of cultivation is guyot, with a distance between rows of 2 m and intra-row of 1 m. The number of vines is 5000 per hectare.

The farm has provided all its hectares of vineyards to the project, as showed in Figure 8.

Pedo-climate information

San Felice extends over 600 hectares, at an altitude of around 400 metres above sea level.

Soil information

The vineyards of “San Felice”, involved in the project, are located in the Soil regions named “RCE: Hilly and mountainous reliefs of central Tuscany, promontories and islands of the archipelago”, APP-Rilievi montuosi dell'Appennino settentrionale e centrale”, “CPL: Internal hilly reliefs originating from Pliocene marine sediments” inside the sub-systems 10, 55, 61, 121, 123, 149 (Figure 9). Table 2 shows the soil characteristics of the different systems and sub-systems of the “San Felice” pilot area.

Figure 8. San Felice vineyards included in the VitiCaSe project

Figure 9 -Soil subsystems in the San Felice vineyards.

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Table 4 - Key Soil Characteristics of San Felice

Soil Region	System	Subsystem	Cartographic Unit
RCE: Hilly and mountainous reliefs of central Tuscany, promontories and islands of the archipelago.	RCE_3. Low-altitude hilly surfaces with moderate slopes, on a substrate consisting mainly of clay, conglomerates and secondarily of sand, with frequent use mainly for agriculture (arable land, olive groves) and secondarily for coppice woodland (Turkey oak, downy oak and holm oak).	10. Slopes with valleys, with a slight to strong slope, subject to moderate to strong diffuse and channeled erosion, with the presence of sub-flat summits and slope shelves, little eroded; substrate mainly consisting of polygenic conglomerates; land use mainly consisting of coppice of downy oak, holm oak, hornbeam and, secondarily, of olive grove and arable land	Soil reference: ABB1 Clay content: 22.47 Organic matter (%): 1.7
			Soil reference: BEL1 Clay content: 24.47 Organic matter (%): 1.7
APP: Mountainous reliefs of the Northern and Central Apennines	APP7. Mountainous surfaces with moderate slopes and hilly surfaces of high and low altitude with moderate to steep slopes, on a substrate consisting mainly of clay with predominantly agricultural use (permanent meadow, arable land, olive grove and vineyard) and secondarily woodland (beech coppice, mixed coppice of thermophilic deciduous broadleaf trees, coniferous forest). Udic and ustic, mesic soil and climate regime.	55. Linear slopes, sometimes terraced, with a low to high gradient, subject to moderate to high widespread water erosion and sometimes to mass erosion; heterogeneous substrate consisting mainly of clays and marls with limestones (Undifferentiated Complex, Chaotic and Scaly Clays); land use consisting mainly of olive groves, vineyards, alternate arable land and, secondarily, pasture, shrubland, mixed forest.	Soil reference: GCC1 Clay content: 29.25 Organic matter (%): 1.5
			Soil reference: ERM1 Clay content: 30.23 Organic matter (%): 1.57
			Soil reference: VIL1 Clay content: 42.57 Organic matter (%): 1.55
	APP_4. Mountainous areas of medium to high altitude, very steep and medium and high-altitude hills with steep slopes, on a substrate consisting of arenaceous pelitic flysch and deposits generated by it, used mainly for forestry (chestnut coppice and beech coppice) and secondarily for	61. Slopes with valleys, from steep to steep, subject to moderate to strong diffuse and channeled surface erosion, with the presence of accumulation areas with lower slope; substrate consisting mainly of sandstones (Macigno type "A"); land use consisting mainly of mixed coppice of deciduous broadleaf trees, secondarily of coniferous woods and, marginally, of arable land and olive groves.	Soil reference: PEL1 Clay content: 11.48 Organic matter (%): 1.67
			Soil reference: GRT1 Clay content: 14.02 Organic matter (%): 2.15

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	agriculture (olive grove, vineyard). Udic and ustic, mesic soil and climate regime.		Soil reference: GRT1 Clay content: 12.17 Organic matter (%): 1.53
CPL: Internal hilly reliefs originating from Pliocene marine sediments	CPL_1: Low-altitude flat surfaces on a substrate consisting mainly of recent and ancient terraced alluvial deposits, used for agricultural purposes (arable land). frequent Ustic and xeric, thermal soil and climate regime.	149. Valley bottoms (of the rivers Arbia, Asso, Orcia, Cecina and Elsa); substrate consisting of fluvial and fluvial-lacustrine deposits; land use consisting very frequently mainly of alternate arable land and meadows.	Soil reference: TAL1 Clay content: 24.08 Organic matter (%): 1.6
	CPL_4. low and medium altitude hilly surfaces, with moderate to steep slopes, on a substrate consisting mainly of Pliocene marine sands, with frequent use mainly for agriculture (olive groves, vineyards and arable land) and secondarily for woodland with downy oak, Turkey oak and holm oak.	121. Slopes with a gentle to moderate gradient, subject to moderate to strong diffuse and channeled water erosion and sometimes to mass erosion; substrate consisting mainly of Pliocene sands; land use consisting mainly of vineyards, olive groves and, secondarily, of rotated arable land.	Soil reference: ARB1 Clay content: 23.18 Organic matter (%): 1.7
APP: Mountainous reliefs of the Northern and Central Apennines	APP_6. High and medium altitude hilly surfaces with moderate to steep slopes, on a substrate mainly composed of marly calcareous flysch, mainly used for coppice woodland (downy oak, Turkey oak) and secondarily for agriculture (olive grove, vineyard). Ustic and udic, mesic soil and climate regime.	123. Incised slopes, moderately sloping to steep, generally eroded to very eroded in the medium-high parts, terraced in the medium-low and low parts; substratum consisting mainly of marly limestones, marlschists and calciferous sandstones (Alberese) and marly limestones (Sillano Formation); land use consisting mainly of vineyards, olive groves, degraded mixed broadleaf forest.	Soil reference: STR1 Clay content: 13.11 Organic matter (%): 1.67
			Soil reference: STR2 Clay content: 12.11 Organic matter (%): 2.07
			Soil reference: CLV1 Clay content: 26.22 Organic matter (%): 2.11
			Soil reference: SOM1 Clay content: 31.37 Organic matter (%): 1.27
			Soil reference: VRZ1 Clay content: 37.45 Organic matter (%): 1.68

The soil organic matter (SOM) in the most representative soils of the different sub-system units ranges from 1.27% to 2.15%, with a clay content varying between 11.48% and 42.57%. According to Table 1, these values indicate that the soils have a low and medium SOC content.

Figure 10 – Soil organic carbon classes in the San Felice vineyards.

Climatic description

The climate in this area is typical hot-summer Mediterranean (Koppen classification: Csa) characterized by warm dry summers, mild winters, and with rainfall mainly concentrated in autumn and spring.

Figure 11 shows the weather conditions from 2013 to 2023. In the last 3 years, the mean temperature has increased, and the precipitation amount has remained at around 800 mm/year. In the period considered, the daily minimum mean temperature was -4,3°C (27/2/2018), the maximum of 29,2 °C (1/8/2017), and the mean temperature of 13,6°C. The mean annual precipitation is 889 mm: the higher annual precipitation was registered in 2014 with 1237 mm, and the minimum in 2015 with 568 mm.

Figure 11 - Annual mean temperature (°C) and rainfall (mm) from 2013 to 2023 in the area.

Management

The farm has the following certifications: Organic, Equalitas, BRC E IFS, ISO 45001; the farm began its conversion to organic farming in 2023.

The farm is covered by multi-risk insurance for its crops.

The practices currently adopted in the vineyard are:

- Spontaneous grassing on 50% of the cultivated hectares:
- Grassing and green manure in alternate rows: one spontaneous row and another with green manure with nitrogen-fixing crops.
- Organic fertilization;
- Use of fungicides and pesticides allowed in organic farming;
- Reuse of wood residues in the field without burning;
- Vineyards are not irrigated;
- The crop operations of pruning, stripping, ploughing, foot cleaning, cage are done manually
- The harvest is both mechanical and manual.

The farm uses third party contractors for the manual management of greenery and dry pruning for 50 ha.

The following man-hours are used to manage the crop each year.

Crop operations	Detailed crop operation	Man hours per hectares
Pruning and crown control	Manual dry pruning	74

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	Ligature of "tralci"	63
	Checkering	35
	Manual pulping	45
	Mechanical shaving	2.5
Soil fertility management and defence	Spreading of fertilizers	1
	Application of fungicides	14
	Application of pesticides	2
Tillage	Processing with ripper	5
	Interrow	10
Maintenance of vineyards	Maintenance of poles and wires	30
Harvest	Manual harvesting	48
	Mechanical harvesting	2
Planting and transplanting	Planting	2.5

Sustainable Soil Management Practice adopted in LIFE VitiCaSe project

The farm chose to adopt the following SSM practice:

- Minimum tillage
- Enhance spontaneous grass cover with Leguminosae
- Improve mulching of pruning residues.

Contact

Manager: Leonardo Bellaccini (Director and oenologist)

Advisor: Lorenzo Fineschi (Agronomist)

Website: <https://www.sanfelice.com/en/wine-estates>

2.3 Farm 3: Rocca di Montemassi

Figure 12 – Rocca di Montemassi farm centre located in Roccastrada (GR).

Site

Rocca di Montemassi is another property of the “Albola” company situated in Roccastrada near Grosseto (Tuscany), whose lands extend over 400 hectares. At Rocca di Montemassi, vine growing, livestock breeding and the production of oil, legumes and cereals coexist: the farm has 106 hectares of vineyards for the production of DOC Maremma Toscana wine, 145 hectares of arable land, 9.5 hectares of olive groves, and a cattle farm.

The farm is certified organic, the main varieties grown are Vermentino and Petit Verdot. The form of breeding is guyot, with a distance between rows of 2.3 m and an intra-row of about 1 m. The number of vines is 4500 per hectare.

The farm has provided approximately 50 hectares of vineyards to the project (Figure 13), of which 21% are planted with Petit Verdot, 20% with Vermentino, 18% with Syrah, 12.6% with Merlot and the remaining with Sangiovese, Cabernet Sauvignon, and Viognier.

Figure 13. Montemassi vineyards included in the VitiCaSe project

Pedo-climate information

Soil information

The “Montemassi” vineyards involved in the project are located in the Soil region named “RCE - Hilly and mountainous reliefs of central Tuscany promontories and islands of the archipelago”, PCO - Coastal plains and hilly reliefs facing the sea” inside the sub-systems 4, 10, 41 and 50 (Figure 14). Table 5 shows the soil characteristics of the different systems and sub-systems of the “Montemassi” pilot area.

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Table 5 - Key Soil Characteristics of the Montemassi pilot area.

Soil Region	System	Subsystem	Cartographic Unit
RCE - Hilly and mountainous reliefs of central Tuscany, promontories and islands of the archipelago.	RCE_3. Low altitude to moderately sloping hilly surfaces, on a substrate consisting mainly of clay, conglomerates and secondarily of sand, used mainly for agriculture (arable land, olive groves) and secondarily for coppice woodland (Turkey oak, downy oak and holm oak).	4. Sub-flat summit surfaces and linear slopes with a gentle slope, subject to moderate widespread water erosion; substrate consisting mainly of marls and sandy lacustrine clays; land use consisting of alternate arable crops and vineyards.	Soil reference: DOG2 Clay content: 29.75 Organic matter (%): 1.22
		10. Slopes with valleys, with a slight to severe gradient, subject to moderate to severe diffuse and channeled erosion, with the presence of sub-flat summits and slope shelves, little eroded; substrate mainly consisting of polygenic conglomerates; land use consisting mainly of coppice woodland of downy oak, holm oak, hornbeam and, secondarily, of olive grove and arable land.	Soil reference: BEL1 Clay content: 22.47 Organic matter (%): 1.76
PCO - Coastal plains and hilly reliefs facing the sea.	PCO_2. Hilly surfaces located at low altitude, from slightly to moderately sloping, on a substrate consisting mainly of ancient terraced fluvial deposits and alluvial fans, used for vineyards and arable crops, and secondarily for coppice and high forest (pine forest, Turkey oak, holm oak). Xeric and ustic soil and climate regime, thermal.	41. Alluvial terraces from sub-flat to slightly sloping, subject to erosion in the residual summit areas; substrate consisting of ancient terraced alluvial deposits; land use consisting mainly of rotated arable land and secondarily of vineyards and olive groves.	Soil reference: DOG2 Clay content: 29.75 Organic matter (%): 1.22
PCO - Coastal plains and hilly reliefs facing the sea.	PCO_1. Flat surfaces located at low altitude, on a substrate consisting mainly of recent alluvial deposits and reclamation by filling, for predominantly agricultural use (arable land, horticultural crops, olive groves). Xeric, thermal soil and climate regime.	50. Flat alluvial areas of the coastal strip (Fine and Albegna rivers); substrate mainly consisting of recent and current alluvial deposits; land use mainly consisting of rotated arable land, horticultural crops and, secondarily, olive groves.	Soil reference: DOM1 Clay content: 33.75 Organic matter (%): 1.98

Figure 14 - Soil subsystems in the Montemassi vineyards.

Figure 15 - SOC content level in the Montemassi vineyards.

The soil organic matter (SOM) in the most representative soils of the different sub-system units ranges from 1.22% to 1.98%, with a clay content varying between 22.4% and 33.7%. According to Table 1, these values indicate that the soils have a low SOC content.

Climatic description

The climate in this area is typical hot-summer Mediterranean (Koppen classification: Csa) characterized by warm dry summers, mild winters, and with rainfall mainly concentrated in autumn and spring.

Figure 16 shows the weather conditions from 2013 to 2023. In the last 3 years, the mean temperature increased, and the precipitation amount decreased to 514 mm/year in 2023. In the period considered, the daily minimum mean temperature was -2°C (27/2/2018), the maximum of 30.3°C (3/8/2017), and the mean temperature of 15.6°C . The mean annual precipitation is 780mm; the higher annual precipitation was registered in 2014 with 1447 mm, and the minimum in 2017 with 440 mm.

Figure 16 - Annual mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and rainfall (mm) from 2013 to 2023 in the area.

Management

The farm holds both Organic and Equalitas certifications and is covered by multi-risk insurance for its crops.

The practices currently adopted in the vineyard are:

- Spontaneous grassing and green manure in alternate rows: one spontaneous row and another with green manure with nitrogen-fixing crops;
- Organic fertilisation: manure application in different areas according to weather conditions;
- Use of pesticides and fungicides allowed in organic farming;
- Minimum tillage;
- Reuse of wood residues in the field without burning;

- Vineyards are irrigated with micro-irrigation system (drip irrigation), water consumption is equal to 20mm/hectare (about 2.5 interventions per year);
- The harvest is both mechanical and manual.

The farm uses third party contractors for the manual management of greenery and dry pruning. The following man-hours are used to manage the crops each year:

Crops operations	Man hours per hectare
Mechanical processing and mechanical treatments	60 hours/hectare
Manual Green Management	130 hours/hectare Of which <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 90 hours/hectare farm• 40 hours/hectare subcontracted
Manual dry pruning	90 hours/hectare Of which <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 70 hours/hectare farm• 20 subcontracted
Ordinary maintenance	30 hours/hectare
Mechanical harvest	7 hours/hectare on 80 hectare
Manual harvest	35 hours/hectare on 25 hectare

Sustainable Soil Management Practice adopted in LIFE VitiCaSe project

The farm chose to adopt the following SSM practice:

- Enhance cover crop of Leguminosae with Graminaceae
- Improve mulching of pruning residues
- Inoculation of mycorrhizae on 50% of the surface
- Manure application on 50% of the surface.

Contact

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3- - Pilot farms in Veneto

3.1 Farm 4: TENUTE RUFFINO S.R.L. SOCIETA' AGRICOLA (RUFFINO)

Figure 17 - Ruffino vineyards.

Site

Tenute Ruffino is a winegrowing company with legal seat in Tuscany region and vineyards located both in Tuscany and Veneto regions (Figure 17).

In the municipality of San Donà di Piave, in the province of Venezia (Veneto region), the farm Ruffino extends over 89 hectares of vineyards for the production of the Prosecco DOCG.

The farm is certified organic, and the main varieties grown are Glera (54% of the area), Pinot Grigio (26%) and Pinot Nero (10%). There are several types of vine cultivation: cordone speronato, sylvoz, doppio capovolto guyot, with a distance between rows of 2.8 m and intra-row of about 1 m.

The farm has provided 50 hectares of vineyards to the project (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Ruffino vineyards included in the Viticas project.

Pedo-climate information

Soil information

The vineyards of “Ruffino”, involved in the project, are located in the soil district named “P-Piave river flood plain with extremely calcareous sediments”. The vineyards are in the soil landscape unit n. P3.3 that is described as a depression of the alluvial plain, mainly composed of clays and silts (Table 5).

Table 6 - Key Soil Characteristics of the Ruffino pilot area.

Soil District	Landscape Overunit	Soil Landscape Unit	Main keys soil properties
P: Piave river flood plain with extremely calcareous sediments.	P3: Ancient low plain (dating back to the last glaciation) with decarbonated soils and accumulation of carbonates in deep horizons.	P3.3: Depressions of the alluvial plain, mainly composed of clays and silts.	Soil reference: BOI1 Clay content: 41 Organic matter (%): 2
			Soil reference: CVZ1 Clay content: 52 Organic matter (%): 2.6

The SOM of the most representative soils of the area ranges from 2% to 2.6%, with a clay content between 41% and 52%. Based on the classifications in Table 1, these values suggest that the soils have a medium SOC content.

Figure 19 - SOC level in the "Ruffino" pilot area

Climatic description

The climate in this area is a humid subtropical climate (Koppen classification: Cfa) characterized by hot and humid summers, and cool to mild winters.

Figure 20 shows the weather conditions from 2013 to 2023. In the last 3 years, the mean temperature has increased, and the precipitation amount decreased by under 1000 mm/year. In

the period considered, the daily minimum mean temperature was -6.1°C (29/12/2014), the maximum of 29°C (5/8/2017), and the mean temperature of 13.6°C.

The mean annual precipitation is 1058 mm; the higher annual precipitation was registered in 2014 with 1841 mm, and the minimum in 2022 with 669 mm.

Figure 20- Annual mean temperature (°C) and rainfall (mm) during the period 2013 and 2023 in the area.

Management

The practices currently adopted in the vineyard during the growing season 2023/24 are:

- Spontaneous grassing on 100% of vineyard surface;
- Organic fertilisation;
- Use of fungicides and pesticides allowed in organic farming;
- Tillage: deep pruning in autumn (at a depth of 40 to 80 cm depending on the vineyard).
- No residue management
- Vineyards are irrigated with a sub-irrigation system: during the growing season 2023/24, the amount of water provided was 1200 mc/ha;
- In recent years, 300 metres of hedges with native plants have been planted to increase biodiversity.

Usually, when climatic conditions are good (autumn not too rainy), grassing with green manure with nitrogen-fixing crops is used on 50% of the cultivated hectares. That is, in alternate rows: one spontaneous row and another with green manure with 1 nitrogen-fixing crop.

The following man-hours are used to manage the crops each year:

Crops operations	Man hours per hectare
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Project number: 101113620

Acronym: LIFE22-CCA-IT-LIFE VitiCaSe

Title: Viticulture for Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration

Co-funded by
the European Union

Mechanical processing and mechanical treatments (soil processing, fertilizer application and defence products)	55h/ha
Manual management of the green	30 h/ha
Mechanical management of the green	3 h/ha
Dry pruning (manual)	60 h/ha
Dry pruning (mechanical)	3 h/ha
Ordinary maintenance	10 h/ha
Mechanical harvesting	2 h/ha

Sustainable Soil Management Practice adopted in LIFE VitiCaSe project

The farm chose to adopt the following SSM practice:

- Enhance spontaneous grass cover with Leguminosae
- Improve green manure
- Inoculation of mycorrhizae
- planting hedges of native plants

Manager: Lorena Troccoli

Advisor: Mattia Tintinaglia (Agronomist)

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